

Phytochemical Analysis, Radical Scavenging Activity and In vitro Pharmacological Activity of Garcinia Cambogia Raw Fruit Extract

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ABSTRACT

Garcinia cambogia (Clusiaceae) is a traditionally used medicinal plant claimed to possess antioxidant properties. Preliminary phytochemical analysis was carried out and the total poly phenol, flavonoid, tannin content was determined using Folin- Ciocalteu's method and flavonoid content was determined by aluminium chloride method and it was quantified using HPTLC method. Free radical scavenging capacity was estimated using DPPH and reducing power method. Substances, which have reduction potential, react with potassium ferricyanide (Fe³⁺) to form Potassium Ferrocyanide (Fe²⁺), which then reacts with Ferric chloride to form ferric ferrous complex that has an absorption maximum at 700 nm. *G. Cambogia* water extract showed a dose dependent antiradical activity by scavenging DPPH radical with an IC₅₀ value of 73.2%. A maximum α -amylase inhibition of 66.37% at a concentration of 320 μ g/ml. Regarding Antihyperlipidemic activity, *G. cambogia* extracts showed inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl CoA (HMG-CoA) reductase, achieving a maximum inhibition of 61.2% at a concentration of 120 μ g/ml. This result implies that the fruit phytoconstituents has the efficacy to maintain and reduce postprandial hyperglycemia, hypercholesterolemia and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production through its biological activities

Keywords: DPPH, Polyphenols, Reducing power, free radicals, flavonoids,

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants based traditional systems of medicines are playing important role in providing health care to large section of population, especially in developing countries. The use of herbal medicinal products and supplements has increased tremendously over the past three decades with not less than 80% of people worldwide relying on them for some part of

primary healthcare [1]. In natural remedies that can be used, among which the major contribution was made by the South Indian fruit, *Garcinia cambogia*, known to people for its use in Indian culinary and folk medicine.[2,3]. *Garcinia* is a plant in the Clusiaceae family, often used for its flavor. It contains different natural compounds like flavonoids and organic acids. One of these acids, called hydroxycitric acid (or (-)

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hydroxycitric acid), is believed to help manage weight and fight obesity.[4]

Garcinia cambogia (Clusiaceae) is a traditionally used medicinal plant claimed to possess antioxidant properties. *Garcinia cambogia*, also known as Malabar tamarind, and known as Garcinia, is a plant native to Southeast Asia. Hydroxycitric acid (HCA), the principal acid of the fruit rind of *Garcinia cambogia* DSER (Hypericaceae), was shown to be a competitive inhibitor of adenosine 59-triphosphate (ATP) citrate lyase, the enzyme that catalyzes the extra mitochondrial cleavage of citrate to oxaloacetate and acetyl CoA.[5] Several antidiabetic drugs are available, but all of them have many adverse side effects such as lactic acidosis, hyper glycemia, diarrhea, or flatulence, which impose an economic burden [6–8]. Therefore, researchers around the world are doing extensive research to find alternative therapies for DM with low side effects and low cost. Medicinal plants and their products have been considered an excellent source for alternative medicine to treat DM by virtue of their active phytochemical constituents. The benefits of a natural medicinal product may be due to a single phytocompound or, more preferably, a synergistic effect of multiple. To date, more than 800 medicinal plants have been reported to show antihyperglycemic activity [9]. The most common benefits of medicinal plants are better safety profiles, good effectiveness, wide availability, acceptability, and affordability [10]. The fruit rinds find its use as a food preservative, flavoring agent, and carminative [11]. Traditionally, it is used for the treatment of constipation, piles, rheumatism, edema, menstrual abnormalities, and parasitic infestations [12].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of fruit extract

Fifty grams of fruits were cleaned and cut into small pieces and boiled in 500mL of water for 15min. The solution was filtered through filter paper in a beaker and cool to room temperature and it is used for phytochemical analysis. It is then evaporated to dryness in water bath and the dried extract is stored in refrigerator for further analysis.

2.2 Preliminary Phytochemical Analysis

Qualitative tests for Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Carbohydrates, Glycosides, Saponins, Tannins, Terpenoids, Proteins and Anthraquinone were performed according to the procedure described by [13]. Mayer's test, Wagner's test for Alkaloids, Shinodas test for flavonoids, Benedicts test & Molisch's test for carbohydrates, Keller-Killani test for cardiac glycosides, froth test for saponins, Lead acetate test for tannins, Salkowski test for terpenoids, Ninhydrin test and Biuret test for protein and Ammonia test for anthraquinone were performed.

2.2.1 Determination of Total Phenol Content:

The total phenol content was determined with the Folin- Ciocalteu's assay using gallic acid as standard. 0.5 mL of plant extract was mixed with 1.5 ml Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (FCR) diluted 1:10 v/v than after 5 minutes, 1.5 ml of 7% sodium carbonate solution was added. The final volume of the tubes was made up to 10 ml with distilled water and allowed to stand for 90 minutes at room temperature. Absorbance of sample was measured against the blank at 750 nm using a spectrophotometer [14].

2.2.2 Determination of Total Flavonoid Content:

Total flavonoid content was determined by Aluminium chloride method using gallic acid as a standard. 1ml of test sample and 4 ml of water was added to a volumetric flask (10 ml volume). Add 0.3 ml of 5 % Sodium nitrite, 0.3 ml of 10% Aluminium chloride was added after 5 minutes. After 6 minutes incubation at room temperature, 1ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide was added to the reaction mixture. Immediately the final volume was made to 10 ml with distilled water. Absorbance of sample was measured against the blank at 510 nm using a spectrophotometer[15].

2.3 High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography Analysis

10 mg sample is dissolved in 10 mL of water and the thin layer chromatography (TLC) is carried out. TLC aluminium sheet precoated with silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates of size 5 X 10 cm, were used. The CAMAG HPTLC instrument consisted of LINOMAT - 5 automated spotter having a 100 µl syringe connected to a nitrogen cylinder, Glass twin – trough developing

chamber 20 X 10cm, viewing cabinet with dual wavelength (254 nm & 366 nm) UV lamps, CAMAG TLC SCANNER 3 with dual wavelength (254 nm & 366 nm) were used for the analysis. Sample was spotted on TLC plates in the form of narrow bands of 8 mm at a distance of 10 mm from the bottom using Camag Linomat 5 spotting instrument. 5 µl of the sample was applied under a continuous dry stream of nitrogen gas. The development of spotted plates was done using two mobile phase Butanol: Acetic acid: Water (7: 2: 1) and Chloroform: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid (5: 4:0.5). The plate was then dried, and the chromatogram was viewed under 254 nm and 366 nm to visualize the phytochemical constituents. The photographs were taken and the digital densitometric scan were done with Camag TLC scanner 3; both 254 nm and 366 nm, operated by win CATS software. Standard preparation was carried out with gallic acid and quercetin at 1mg/1ml concentration [16].

2.4 In vitro antioxidant studies

2.4.1 DPPH Radical Scavenging activity

Determination of DPPH scavenging activity was carried out according to [17]. DPPH was dissolved in methanol. This has an absorption band at 515 nm which disappears on reduction by an antioxidant compound. An aliquot of the extract was added to 1.5 mL of freshly prepared DPPH solution (0.25g/L in methanol). After 20 minutes of incubation absorbance was measured at 515nm. The percentage of DPPH remaining in the solution can be calculated. 100 minus the DPPH remaining value will give the amount of DPPH scavenged [18].

2.4.2 Reducing Power Method

The reducing power of *Garcinia Cambogia* methanolic extract was determined by the slight modification [19]. Various concentrations of the extracts in corresponding solvents were mixed with phosphate buffer (2.5 mL) and potassium ferricyanide (2.5 mL). This mixture was kept at 50°C in water bath for 20 minutes. After cooling, 2.5 mL of 10% trichloro acetic acid was added and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min whenever necessary. The upper layer of solution (2.5 mL) was mixed with distilled water (2.5 mL) and a freshly prepared ferric chloride solution (0.5 mL). The absorbance was measured at 700 nm.

Ascorbic acid at various concentrations was used as standard.

2.5. Determination of In vitro Pharmacological Studies

2.5.1 α-Amylase Inhibition Study: The α-amylase inhibitory activity of the test sample (CVC) was evaluated using a slightly modified standard procedure [20]. Different concentrations of the test sample (10, 20, 40, 80, 160, and 320 µg/mL), the reference standard (Acarbose), and a control (without the test sample or standard) were mixed with a solution of α-amylase (100µL, 0.1mg/mL). The reaction mixtures were pre-incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes. Subsequently, 100 µL of starch solution was added to initiate the enzymatic reaction, and the incubation was continued at 37°C for 60 minutes. Each tube was filled with 100 µL of iodine reagent and 10 µL of 1 M HCl to stop the reaction. At 565 nm, the final solution's absorbance was measured.

The α-amylase inhibitory activity was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{\text{OD of Control} - \text{OD of test}}{\text{OD of Control}} \times 100$$

In this method, the optical density (OD) of control refers to the absorbance measured for the control sample (lacking the test sample or standard). At the same time, the OD of the test denotes the absorbance of the sample at different concentrations. The α-amylase inhibitory potential of CVC is determined by comparing the absorbance values of the test samples with those of the control [20].

2.5.2 β-Hydroxy β-methylglutaryl-CoA (HMG-CoA inhibitory assay): The spectrophotometric approach evaluated the test sample's (CVC) HMG-CoA reductase inhibitory assay activity. A reaction mixture including 60 µl of NADPH (400µM), HMG CoA Substrate (400 µM), and potassium phosphate buffer (100 mM, pH7.4) containing KCl (120 mM), EDTA (1 mM), and DTT (5 mM) was mixed with extract samples of various concentrations. After 10 minutes of incubation at 37°C, the absorbance at 340 nm was measured for the reaction mixture. Atorvastatin was used as a positive control.

% inhibition = $\frac{\text{OD of Control} - \text{OD of test}}{\text{OD of Control}} \times 100$

OD of Control

This formula compares the optical density of the test sample to that of the control to quantify the test sample's inhibitory effect on HMG-CoA reductase [21].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Phytochemical analysis

Preliminary phytochemical analysis showed the presence of tannins, saponins, flavonoids steroids anthraquinones. Total polyphenol content was estimated and found to be 76.56 ± 0.07 Tannic Acid Equivalent, (TAE) per g of dry weight. The total flavonoid content was found to be 0.15 ± 0.03 , Gallic Acid Equivalents. (GAE)

Fig.1 Under Visible light & U.V light

Fig 2 Using Anisaldehyde-Sulphuric acid Reagent

Fig .3 HPTLC chromatogram of *water* extract, Standard Gallic acid and Quercetin

Peak	Start Position	Start Height	Max Position	Max Height	Max %	End Position	End Height	Area	Area %
1	0.04 Rf	8.4 AU	0.11 Rf	48.7 AU	19.59 %	0.17 Rf	0.2 AU	2872.6 AU	33.44 %
2	0.18 Rf	1.2 AU	0.22 Rf	18.8 AU	7.56 %	0.25 Rf	14.8 AU	657.4 AU	7.65 %
3	0.29 Rf	21.4 AU	0.31 Rf	27.7 AU	11.13 %	0.34 Rf	15.3 AU	756.4 AU	8.81 %
4	0.34 Rf	16.4 AU	0.36 Rf	20.8 AU	8.38 %	0.40 Rf	2.8 AU	585.9 AU	6.82 %
5	0.74 Rf	0.2 AU	0.78 Rf	20.6 AU	8.28 %	0.82 Rf	0.5 AU	711.3 AU	8.28 %
6	0.86 Rf	0.2 AU	0.91 Rf	112.0 AU	45.05 %	0.94 Rf	6.5 AU	3005.6 AU	34.99 %

Peak	Start Position	Start Height	Max Position	Max Height	Max %	End Position	End Height	Area	Area %
1	0.84 Rf	3.4 AU	0.90 Rf	243.5 AU	100.00 %	0.96 Rf	6.5 AU	12984.8 AU	100.00 %

Peak	Start Position	Start Height	Max Position	Max Height	Max %	End Position	End Height	Area	Area %
1	0.74 Rf	1.2 AU	0.85 Rf	189.4 AU	100.00 %	0.88 Rf	1.3 AU	8220.7 AU	100.00 %

Fig 4: Peak display & % area of *Garcinia Cambogia* water extract, Standard Gallic acid and Quercetin

Fig 5: Densitogram of tracks at 254nm

The above peak table 4, compares the standard gallic acid and quercetin with the extract of *Garcinia*

cambogia water extract. It is found that in the solvent system butanol, acetic acid, water t six peaks were present which shows six compounds. Out of this track 1, track 2, track 3, track 5, track 6 was that of tannic acid (1mg/mL) gallic acid and the extract showed the same Rf at peak and it was found to be present to 8.26% with 711 AU area and the next standard was found to be matching with 0.86 Rf which is of comparable range with standard Quercetin and found to be observed 34.99% with 3005.6 AU area.

3.2 Reducing Power Method & DPPH radical scavenging activity

Fig:6

Fig :7

The water extract of *G.cambogia* showed a dose dependent antiradical activity by scavenging DPPH radical with an IC₅₀ value of 73.2% (Fig.6). Presence of reducers causes the conversion of the Fe³⁺/Ferricyanide complex used in this method to the ferrous form. By measuring the formation of Pearl's Prussian blue at 700nm, it is possible to determine the concentration of Fe³⁺ ion. Higher absorbance of the reaction mixture indicates higher reductive potential (Fig.7). Substances, which have reduction potential, react with potassium ferricyanide (Fe³⁺) to form Potassium Ferrocyanide (Fe²⁺), which then reacts with Ferric chloride to form ferric ferrous complex which has an absorption maximum at 700 nm.

3.3 Determination of *In vitro* antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic activity

This in-vitro study on the *G. cambogia*, reveals its promising potential in managing T2DM through its

notable antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic properties. Calcium-containing α -amylase in the oral cavity, serum α amylase in the gut, and α -glucosidase in the small intestine maintain postprandial hyperglycemia by inhibiting carbohydrate digestion and glucose regulation [22]. Both *G. cambogia* fruit extracts exhibited potent inhibitory effects on α -amylase enzymes regarding antidiabetic activity. A maximum α -amylase inhibition of 66.37% at a concentration of 320µg/ml (Fig 8). This substantial inhibition indicates that *G. cambogia* extracts effectively impede the enzymatic breakdown of complex carbohydrates into polysaccharides, oligosaccharides, disaccharides and monosaccharides. By slowing down this process, *G. cambogia* can reduce the digestion and absorption rate of carbohydrates, thereby mitigating postprandial glucose spikes a key factor in managing blood sugar levels.

Diabetes mellitus associated with lipid changes is attributed to insulin resistance-induced free fatty acid flux [23]. Diabetic Dyslipidemia is defined as high plasma triglyceride concentration with low HDL cholesterol levels and increased concentration of small dense LDL cholesterol particles. Regarding Antihyperlipidemic activity, *G. cambogia* extracts showed inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl CoA (HMG-CoA) reductase, achieving a maximum inhibition of 61.2% at a concentration of 120 μ g/ml (Fig 9). HMG-CoA reductase plays an essential role in cholesterol biosynthesis by catalysing the rate-

limiting step in the production of cholesterol within the liver. Specifically, this enzyme converts HMG CoA to mevalonate, a precursor of cholesterol [24]. This step is crucial because it is one of the primary regulatory points in the cholesterol synthesis pathway, determining the rate at which cholesterol is produced. This inhibition leads to a decrease in the production of mevalonate and subsequent cholesterol. As a result, the liver's ability to produce cholesterol is diminished. This reduction in hepatic cholesterol synthesis subsequently lowers the blood's circulating cholesterol levels [25,26].

CONCLUSION

Herbal medicine has become an integral part of standard healthcare, based on a combination of time-honored traditional usage and ongoing scientific research. Burgeoning interest in medicinal herbs has increased scientific scrutiny of their therapeutic potential and safety. HPTLC analysis gives an idea of the quantification of phytoconstituents when compared with standard and this gives more specificity regarding the phytoconstituents present in it and throws light towards the active constituents. Compounds with reducing power indicate that they are electron donors and can reduce the oxidized intermediates of lipid peroxidation processes, so that they can act as primary and secondary antioxidants. DPPH also shows the potential to scavenge the radicals. Although establishing the mechanisms behind these effects is far beyond the scope of this study, we can certainly mention that the phytoconstituents of *G. cambogia* might be

responsible for these pharmacological properties. We can conclude that *G. cambogia* is a nontoxic source of natural antioxidants that could be used to treat diabetes and its complications. However, more detailed biochemical and molecular studies should be conducted to identify the main active ingredients in *G. cambogia* and their mechanistic roles as well.

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